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Rahim Thawer - Queer Mental Health Media Archive

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Abstract

This interview details harm reduction counseling as a respectful, non-abstinence-based approach to addressing substance use and other high-risk behaviors within LGBTQIA+ inclusive care. It emphasizes meeting clients where they are, using tools like motivational interviewing and the ABC model (Activators, Behavior, Consequences) to collaboratively identify negative outcomes and create realistic, incremental change goals. The approach validates relapse as part of recovery and focuses on reducing harms while understanding the social and emotional functions of the behavior.

Keywords

clinical practice, cultural competence, support

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